

**TEACHER LEVEL FACTORS AFFECTING QUALITY OF
INSTRUCTION IN LAS NIEVES DISTRICT II,
DIVISION OF AGUSAN DEL NORTE**

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By

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APPROVAL SHEET

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ABSTRACT

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Abstract

This study sought to determine the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction in Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. The respondents' profile and the factors affecting quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time and assessment were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire. Further, the significant difference between school heads' and teachers' responses was tested. The significant association between respondents' profile and the factors affecting quality of instruction was also verified.

The researcher used both descriptive and comparative research design in conducting the study. Purposive sampling was used to determine the eight school heads and 91 teacher-respondents from public elementary schools of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. After considering the problems, frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Mann-Whitney U-test, Chi-square test, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were used to analyze the data.

The result revealed that majority of the respondents belong to the middle bracket age. As to educational attainment, most of the respondents were not able to pursue post graduate studies. As to years in service, most of the respondents were new in the teaching profession. As to factors affecting quality of instruction, the teachers' and school heads' responses revealed that teachers sometimes demonstrated these factors except for orientation of learners and management of

time which were seldom done by teachers. It also revealed that assessment was often done by teachers. It was further revealed that teachers' and school heads' responses on the factors affecting quality of instruction were not significantly different. As to the respondents' profile, only educational attainment has a significant association with the factors affecting the quality of instruction.

It is recommended that the Department of Education may conduct trainings on how teachers can further improve quality of instruction especially on assessment. School administrators must intensify instructional supervision and give feedback on the performances of teachers so that teachers are guided on their areas that need improvement. Teachers are encouraged to undertake trainings which would upgrade their competences with regards to quality instruction. Lastly, a further study may be made by the future researchers to explore more variables which was not included in the present study.

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CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

Introduction

Our education system seeks to provide quality education for all types of learners, hence, quality instruction is very crucial in developing learners. Quality instruction refers to the delivery of instruction in a way that arouses students' interest, critical thinking, and learning in a meaningful way. It makes students curious and excited about what they are doing and consequently enabling them to discover learning and take ownership of their education. In such, quality instruction is being provided to promote life-long learning of students.

In this connection, teachers take pride when hearing the successes of their learners which is the proof of quality instruction. However, poor quality instruction may lead to dissatisfaction of learners to learn (Sogunro, 2017).

Teachers need enough strength of character and technique to ensure an orderly, friendly, and productive classroom. Teachers need to be willing to continuously improve their practices by building their content and pedagogical knowledge. Teachers must also explore ways on how to use effective materials and how to work productively with their colleagues. Proficient teachers accomplish these goals in a variety of ways, depending on their unique personalities and approaches, but most successful practitioners have mastered the entire range of skills (Honig, 2011).

Moreover, teachers' instruction must have appropriate expectations on learners' capabilities and group them accordingly. Teachers should use time effectively, provide active teaching, teach with clarity and enthusiasm. Teachers must also align instructional and curricular pace with the K to 12 curricula. Teach with mastery of the topic and lastly, have effective review and feedback after the discussion (Lavigne and Good, 2014).

To promote quality of instruction, DepEd Order No.39, series of 2016 entitled, Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda provides some themes that underscore the agenda. One of these is the teaching and learning process. Under the teaching and learning, is the sub-theme instruction which teachers take into consideration to provide quality of instruction.

Based on the readings, the researcher is encouraged to study the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction in Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. This study aimed to help review the needs of teachers in improving classroom instruction. This would also give an insight to the Department of Education on what to do with the present scenario with regards on enhancing the quality of instruction of teachers.

Theoretical Framework

This research is related to the Dynamic Model of Educational Effectiveness (Creemers and Kyriakides, 2010). This model is an evidence-based and theory-driven approach. The recommended approach to school improvement gives emphasis to quality of teaching and to conditions created at different levels for improving the quality of teaching. This model is subdivided into four levels. These are the system level factor, school level factor, teacher level factor and student level factor. These levels play a crucial part in teaching and learning process. The system level factors refer to the influence of the educational system through a more formal way, especially through developing and evaluating the educational policies at the national or regional level. The school level factor is concerned with the school policies which mainly refer to the actions taken by the school to help teachers and other stakeholders have a clear understanding of what is expected from them to do. Teacher level factor is subdivided into eight factors, these are orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time and assessment. The last level is the student level factor which is categorized into three. These are socio-cultural and economical background variables (e.g. socio-economic status, sex, ethnicity and personal traits), psychological perspective background variables (e.g. subject motivation, thinking style and expectations), and learning task variables (e.g.

aptitude, perseverance, time on task and opportunity to learn). Every factor covers some elements of quality of instruction.

Out of these factors of the dynamic model of educational effectiveness, only the teacher level factors were taken as dependent variables. This study is all about the teacher level factors affecting the quality of instructions in Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. The independent variable is the teacher respondents' profile in terms of age, educational attainment and years in service and the dependent variables are the factors affecting quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time and assessment.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram showing the interplay of variables.

Statement of the Problem

This research sought to find out the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction in Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte.

Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' profile in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Educational Attainment
 - 1.3. Years in service
2. What are the factors affecting the quality of instruction of teachers as to:
 - 2.1. Orientation of Learners
 - 2.2. Structuring of Lesson
 - 2.3. Questioning
 - 2.4. Teaching Modelling
 - 2.5. Application of Learnings
 - 2.6. Classroom as a Learning Environment
 - 2.7. Management of Time
 - 2.8. Assessment
3. Is there a significant difference between the teachers' and school heads' responses as to the factors affecting the quality of instruction?
4. Which of the independent variables singly or in combination affects the teachers' quality of instruction?
5. What intervention can be made based on the findings of the study?

Hypotheses

H_{0_1} : There is no significant difference between the teachers' and school heads' responses as to the factors affecting the quality of instruction.

H_{0_2} : None of the independent variables singly or in combination affects the teachers' quality of instruction.

Scope and Delimitation

This study is focused on the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction in Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. The respondents were the 8 school heads and 91 elementary school teachers of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte, school year 2019-2020. The independent variables were limited to the teacher respondents' profile in terms of age, educational attainment and years in service. The age of the teacher-respondents ranges from 20 to 60 years old while educational attainment of teachers refers to post graduate (Ph.D. or Master's Degree Holders), college graduate and those with Master of Arts units. Also, years in service ranges from 1 to 40 years. School heads' profile were not included in the independent variables. The dependent variables were limited to factors of quality instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time and assessment.

Definition of terms

The following words and phrases were operationally defined for a clearer and better understanding of the study.

Application of Learnings. This is one of the factors affecting quality of instruction that focuses on how teachers use differentiated activities as seatwork or small group tasks that help students apply the concept and skills learned.

Assessment. This term is focuses on how teachers use appropriate techniques to collect data on students' knowledge and skills and analyze these data in order to identify students' needs.

Classroom as a learning environment. This phrase focused on the teachers' way of establishing task behaviors through interactions (i.e. teacher-student and student-student interactions) and depreciate students' misbehaviors.

Elements. These are the indicators of each factors of quality instructions.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction. This phrase refers to the factors that might affect the quality instruction at the teachers' level.

Management of time. It is one of the factors affecting quality of instruction that focuses on how teachers manage their time in a classroom environment.

Orientation of Learners. This term is one of the factors affecting quality of instruction that focuses on how teachers provide objectives for specific task and how they challenge the students to identify the reason why an activity exists.

Quality Instruction. It is defined as the degree to which an instruction is adequately delivered, meets students' learning needs, learning styles, interests, expectations, and is well aligned to standards.

Questioning. This is one of the factors affecting quality of instruction that focuses on teachers' way of delivering questions to students and how they raised different types of questions at appropriate levels.

School Head. This term refers to the school leader who manages public elementary schools.

Structuring of Lesson. This phrase focuses on how to organize and outline lesson parts in teaching and learning and how they review main ideas of the lesson.

Teacher Level Factors. These are the eight teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction namely: orientation of learners; structuring of lesson; questioning; teaching modelling; application of learnings; classroom as a learning environment; management of time; and assessment.

Teacher respondents' profile. This phrase refers to the age, educational attainment and years in service of the respondents. These were gathered through the survey questionnaire.

Teaching Modelling. This is one of the factors affecting quality of instruction that focuses on how teachers provide the learners with different modelling strategies.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents some related literature and studies that are directly or indirectly related to the present study.

Related Literature

According to Darling-Hammond (2010) in her article *Teacher Quality and Student Achievement: A Review of State Policy Evidence*, using data from a 50-state survey of policies, state case study analyses, the 1993-94 Schools and Staffing Surveys (SASS), and the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), examines the ways in which teacher qualifications and other school inputs are related to student achievement across states. The findings of both the qualitative and quantitative analyses suggest that policy investments in the quality of teachers may be related to improvements in student performance. Quantitative analyses indicate that measures of teacher preparation and certification are by far the strongest correlates of student achievement in reading and mathematics, both before and after controlling for student poverty and language status. This analysis suggests that policies adopted by states regarding teacher education, licensing, hiring, and professional development may make an important difference in the qualifications and capacities that teachers bring to their work.

Another article which focuses on Classroom Process Quality examined the interplay between curriculum-embedded formative assessment—a well-

known teaching practice—and general features of classroom process quality like cognitive activation, supportive climate, classroom management - and their combined effect on elementary school students' understanding of the scientific concepts of floating and sinking. Curriculum-embedded formative assessment and classroom process quality promoted students' learning. Moreover, classroom process quality and embedded formative assessment interacted in promoting student learning. To ensure effective instruction and consequently satisfactory learning outcomes, teachers need to combine specific teaching practices with high classroom process quality (Decristan, Klieme, Kunter, Hochweber, Büttner, Fauth and Hardy ,2015).

Horn and Jang (2017) stated that teachers who earn their advanced degrees show a deep level of understanding and commitment to the profession, allowing them to modify curriculum goals, adjust teaching methods, and enter leadership positions to enact the system-wide changes in education they wish to see.

Kennedy (2010) in his article, Attribution Error and the Quest for Teacher Quality, suggests that education researchers and policy makers may be overestimating the role of personal qualities in their quest to understand teaching quality. In their effort to understand classroom-to-classroom differences in student learning, researchers focus too much on the characteristics or personal traits of teachers, overlooking situational predictors like school policies and school learning environment.

Pintrich and Schunk (2012) stated in their article that setting objectives is the process of establishing a direction to guide learning. Moreover, when teachers communicate objectives for student learning, students can see more easily the connections between what they are doing in class and what they are supposed to learn. Further, students can gauge their starting point in relation to the learning objectives and determine what they need to pay attention to and where they might need help from the teacher or others. This clarity helps decrease anxiety about their ability to succeed.

Meyer, Rose and Gordon (2014) suggests that well-structured lesson framing, helps teachers to organize the lesson, allow for a smoother functioning classroom, classroom disruptions are minimized, the stress on the teacher is reduced, and the learning environment is optimized for students. This will lead to good teaching quality.

Sockalingam (2011) specified that teachers need to have a clear intent for questioning and also learn to ask the right questions. To guide students on the learning process, it is essential to question on learning outcome as well as students' thinking and learning processes. Through this, the student will learn to answer the questions being thrown to them without hesitation and thus, provide quality instruction.

The Room 241 Team (2015) expressed that each student is different, and when it comes to learning styles, the ones that prove the most effective depend on who is being taught. One of the ways in which teachers can maximize the

effectiveness of their time in the classroom is to rotate the types of instruction being used, making sure that there is a mix of strategies that might work well for different students. By combining a few different types of modelling activities, teachers make the classroom a dynamic place to learn and keep their students engaged with the modelling activities.

As said by Relajo-Howell (2017) that by bringing the real world to the classroom setting will make students more lively and quality instruction takes place. Moreover, he further explains that by permitting the students to apply what they have learned, they will tend to master those learning.

In addition, Luukkonen (2011) states that bringing the real world inside the classroom is like breaking distinctions among texts and real – life objects. Students will learn best when they can see, touch or smell the object itself.

Slavin (2014) concludes in his article that collaboration is the process by which learners interact in small groups to learn. Further, he stated that within a group, different strengths and weaknesses were shown, thus, helping one another will lead to significant learning.

Verner (2018) clearly stated that it is important to both teachers and learners to be time-bounded. But the necessities are within the teachers' control. Teacher gives their students instructions at the start of each activity, and make sure that the instructions are brief but clear.

According to Guskey and Jung (2013), teachers who develop useful assessments, provide corrective instruction, and give students second chances to demonstrate success can improve their instruction and help students learn.

Bichi (2017) added that in turn, the effective monitoring and evaluation of teaching is central to the continuous improvement of the quality of instruction of teachers in a school. It is essential to know the strengths of teachers and those aspects of their practice which could be further developed. From this perspective, teacher evaluation is a vital step in the drive to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning and raise educational standards.

According to Bodhe and Jankar (2013) that age regardless of young or old has potential to be a good teacher. Furthermore, as long as teachers can teach enthusiastically with effective communication and problem solving skills, there should be no problem.

Sawchuk (2015) specified that though at first, years in service has impact to quality instruction, but later on, gained experiences would not be enough to associate with the quality of teaching.

Related Studies

Huang and Moon (2010) stated that total years of service was not significantly associated with teachers' performance as they noted that while 3% of the examined studies actually indicated a negative association between teachers' years of experience and teachers' performance, and 30% indicated a positive association which usually for only the first few years of teaching, the

majority 67% showed no correlation between teachers' years of experience and teachers' performance.

According to Nilsen and Gustafsson (2016), input and process characteristics of schooling are related to students' achievement. The researchers hypothesized that teacher quality predicts instructional quality and student learning outcome. These hypotheses were investigated by applying multi-level structural equation modelling to grade four student and teacher data from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2011. The sample included 205,515 students from 47 countries nested in 10,059 classrooms. Results revealed that teacher quality was significantly related to instructional quality and student achievement, whereas student achievement was not well predicted by instructional quality. The results are varied in some countries. Participation in professional development activities and teachers' sense of preparedness were, on average, the strongest predictors of instructional quality across all countries. Professional development was of particular relevance in Europe and Western Asian/Arabian countries, whereas, preparedness played an important role in instructional quality in South-East Asia and Latin America. Also, the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) announced the level of teacher education was on average the strongest predictor of student achievement across all countries; this characteristic mattered most in the Western Asia/Arabia region.

According to Vandersall, Vruwink, and LaVenia (2012), teachers who earn master's degrees demonstrate greater teaching effectiveness than those who don't. The study found out that students whose teachers held a master's degree performed better in reading and writing tests.

In the work of Gore, Lloyd, Smith, Bowe, Ellis and Lubans (2017), strong evidence of the effectiveness of professional development for teachers is limited. This study tested a pedagogy-based, collaborative Professional Development or PD approach for impact on the quality of teaching. A cluster randomized controlled trial involving eight teachers at each of 24 schools found significant positive effects on quality ($d = 0.4$), independent of school type (primary/secondary), school location (urban/rural), and years of teaching experience. These effects were sustained six months later. Qualitative data are used to illustrate mechanisms behind the success of the intervention. This study illuminates how to support teacher learning for measurable positive impacts on quality teaching. In addition, quality of instruction may vary depending on the educational background of the teacher.

Moreover, according to the study of Alvarez (2018), teacher quality has significant relationship to the quality of instruction. By recognizing the connection between quality teaching and quality instruction, his study explained how observable teacher characteristics are related to the teachers' quality instruction, this study concluded that some observable teacher quality characteristics such

as the educational background, certification & training status and professional development activities are significantly related to the quality of instruction.

Another study about teacher quality which impacts academic achievement was done by Goe (2017). This research focused only on studies in which he tied the findings explicitly to teacher quality. Goe's analysis revealed four lenses for examining teacher quality. These are teacher qualifications, teacher characteristics, teacher practices and teacher effectiveness. These four lenses test the quality of the teacher and significantly affect the teachers' quality of instruction.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the research design, research locale, the research respondents, sampling procedure, research instrument, ethical standard, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment of the study.

Research Design

The researcher used both descriptive and comparative research design in conducting the study. Descriptive because it described the teachers' profile and the factors affecting quality of instruction. Comparative research design since it determined the significant difference between the school heads and teachers' responses on the factors affecting quality of instruction. It also tests the significant association between the teachers' profile and the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the eight public elementary schools of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. The location of the schools is shown in, Figure 2. The eight elementary schools are as follows: Lingayao Elementary School, Maningalao Elementary School, Kahayagan Elementary School, Mat-i Central Elementary School, Pinana-an Elementary School, Dalagangan Elementary School, Ambacon Elementary School and E.G. Montilla Elementary School. Lingayao Elementary School, Maningalao Elementary

School and Mat-i Central Elementary School are located along the highway. The remaining six schools are located in the interior part of the district.

Research Respondents

The respondents were eight school heads and 91 teachers of the identified schools. Specifically, nine teachers each came from the elementary schools of Ambacon, Dalagangan and Pinana-an. Eleven teachers were from E.G. Montilla Elementary School, six from Kahayagan Elementary School, 17 from Lingayao Elementary School, 10 from Maningalao Elementary School and 20 from Mat-i Central Elementary School.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents

School	School head	Teachers	Teacher-respondents percentage (%)
Ambacon Elementary School	1	9	10
Dalagangan Elementary School	1	9	10
E.G. Montilla Elementary School	1	11	12
Kahayagan Elementary School	1	6	7
Lingayao Elementary School	1	17	19
Maningalao Elementary School	1	10	11
Mat-i Central Elementary School	1	20	21
Pinana-an Elementary School	1	9	10
Total	8	91	100%

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents in the public elementary schools of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte. The respondents include both school heads and elementary teachers.

Sampling Procedure

In choosing the total respondents, purposive sampling was used to determine the eight school heads and 91 teacher respondents coming from the eight public elementary schools of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a researcher-made survey questionnaire to collect the necessary data for this study. Block I consists of teacher-respondents' profile which included their age that ranges from 20 up to 60 years old, educational attainment which refers to post graduate, college graduate and with master's degree units and years in service that ranges from one up to 40 years. Block II consists of the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction which includes eight factors. These factors were on the orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as learning environment, management of time and assessment. All teacher level factors have six elements that serves as the indicators.

For the scoring and quantification of data in Block II, the following scale was used:

Rating Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Description
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always Demonstrated
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often Demonstrated
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes Demonstrated
2	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom Demonstrated
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Demonstrated at All

Ethical Standards

The researcher assured the respondents that the data gathered for the accomplished questionnaires will be treated with utmost confidentiality. The researcher maintained the highest level of objectivity in the discussion and analysis throughout the research.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent. After the Superintendent's approval, concerned school heads and principals were informed about the conduct of the study. The researcher arranged schedules for the administration of the questionnaires. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires and gave instructions to all the respondents. Enough time was given to the respondents to answer the survey questionnaires. After completion, the researcher gathered the survey questionnaires, tallied and tabulated all the data. Later, all the gathered data were submitted to the statistician for the appropriate

statistical treatment. Analysis and interpretation of the data was done by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

Guided by the problem and hypotheses posed in the study, the researcher used the following statistical tools with 95% confidence level or $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

Frequency and Percentage. This was used to determine the respondents' profile in terms of age, educational attainment and years in service.

Weighted Mean. This tool was used to measure the responses of teachers and school heads on the factors affecting quality of instruction.

Mann-Whitney U-Test. A type of comparative analysis used to determine if there is a significant difference between the teachers' and school heads' responses on the factors affecting quality of instruction.

Chi-Square Test. This tool was used to determine the significant association between teachers' profile and the factors affecting quality of instruction.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. This tool was used to determine if the data is a parametric or a non-parametric type.

CHAPTER IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter shows the analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the teachers and school heads of the nine public elementary schools of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte regarding the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction.

Problem 1. What is the respondents' profile in terms of age, educational attainment, sex, socio-economic status and years of service?

Profile of the Teacher Respondents as to Age

Table 2

Distribution of Teacher Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
20-30 Years old	21	23
31-40 Years Old	27	30
41-50 Years Old	26	29
51-60 Years Old	17	18
Total	91	100%

Table 2 presents the number of teacher respondents as to their age bracket. As shown in the Table, out of 91 respondents, 27 teacher respondents

or 30 were 31 – 40 years old which is the highest number of frequency. On the other hand, 17 teacher respondents or 22 percent belong to the age bracket of 51 – 60 years old. This implies that majority of the teacher respondents were middle – aged.

**Profile of the Respondents
as to Educational Attainment**

Table 3

Distribution of Teacher Respondents as to Educational Attainment

Educational attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Post Graduate	20	22
College Graduate	38	42
With MA Units	33	36
Total	91	100%

Table 3 presents the number of teacher respondents as to their educational attainment. As shown in the Table, out of 91 respondents, 38 teacher respondents or 42 percent are college graduates. There were 33 teacher respondents or 36 percent who have MA units but they were not able to finish the degree. Lastly, only 20 teacher respondents or 22% were post graduate teachers. This implies that most of the teacher respondents were not able to pursue post graduate studies.

**Profile of the Teacher Respondents
as to Years in Service**

Table 4

Distribution of Teacher Respondents as to Years in Service

Years in service	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1-10 Years	42	46
11-20 Years	39	43
21-30 Years	7	8
31-40 Years	3	3
Total	91	100%

Table 4 presents the number of teacher respondents as to their years in service. As shown in the table, out of 91 respondents, 42 teacher respondents or 46 percent had 1-10 years in the service. On the other hand, only three teachers or three percent were already 31-40 years in service. This implies that most of the teachers in Las Nieves II were new in the service.

Problem 2. What are the factors affecting the quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time and assessment?

**Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction
as to Orientation of Learners**

Table 5

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Orientation of Learners

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Provide students with aims/goals of lessons to take place.	2.53	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.49	Seldom Demonstrated
Link the day's lesson to previous lesson or students' daily life.	2.32	Seldom Demonstrated	2.29	Seldom Demonstrated
Present the aims in different stages in accordance with the flow of the activities.	2.65	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.59	Sometimes Demonstrated
Offer clear and understandable aims for students.	2.26	Seldom Demonstrated	2.23	Seldom Demonstrated
Provide different ways of presenting the aims in response to different background of students.	2.21	Seldom Demonstrated	2.27	Seldom Demonstrated
Challenge students to identify reasons for an activity.	2.19	Seldom Demonstrated	2.21	Seldom Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.36	Seldom Demonstrated	2.35	Seldom Demonstrated

As shown in Table 5, teachers in Las Nieves District II seldom orient their learners on the objectives of the lesson with an average weighted mean of 2.36 as rated by teachers and 2.35 as evaluated by school heads. The highest weighted means of 2.65 and 2.59 by teachers and school heads respectively

revealed that the aims of the lesson are sometimes presented in different stages in accordance with the flow of the activities. The lowest weighted means of 2.26 and 2.23 indicate that the teachers seldom offered clear and understandable aims for students. This implies that students are not well-oriented on the objectives of the lesson.

Pintrich and Schunk (2012) emphasized that setting objectives is the process of establishing a direction to guide learning. Moreover, when teachers communicate objectives for student learning, students can see more easily the connections between what they are doing in class and what they are supposed to learn. They can gauge their starting point in relation to the learning objectives and determine what they need to pay attention to and where they might need help from the teacher or others. This clearly helps decrease anxiety about their ability to succeed.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Structuring of Lesson

Table 6 presents that teachers in Las Nieves District II are rated sometimes when it comes to structuring of the lesson with an average weighted mean of 2.91 as rated by teachers and 2.89 as evaluated by school heads. Respectively, the highest weighted means of 4.10 and 4.08 revealed that the transition between one phase/activity and others are often presented. On the other hand, the lowest weighted means of 1.45 and 1.43 shows that teachers rarely presented the structure of the lesson.

Table 6

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Structuring of Lesson

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Begin with overview of objectives.	2.29	Seldom Demonstrated	2.26	Seldom Demonstrated
Present the structure of the lesson.	1.45	Not Demonstrated at All	1.43	Not Demonstrated at All
Explain the link among different activities.	3.35	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.32	Sometimes Demonstrated
Signal the transition between one phase/activity and others.	4.10	Often Demonstrated	4.08	Often Demonstrated
Outline content of the lesson.	2.51	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.60	Sometimes Demonstrated
Review main ideas.	3.80	Often Demonstrated	3.70	Often Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.91	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.89	Sometimes Demonstrated

This implies that the teachers rarely show the parts of the whole lesson.

Meyer, Rose and Gordon (2014) suggested that well-structured lesson framing, helps teachers to organize the lesson, allow for a smoother functioning classroom, class room disruptions are minimized, the stress on the teacher is reduced, and the learning environment is optimized for students. This will lead to good teaching quality.

**Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction
as to Questioning**

Table 7

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Questioning

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Raise questions at appropriate difficulty levels.	3.08	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.99	Sometimes Demonstrated
Has clear intent in questioning.	2.56	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.54	Sometimes Demonstrated
Give students enough time to respond.	4.53	Always Demonstrated	4.48	Often Demonstrated
Give positive and constructive comments or feedback to students' responses.	2.66	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.70	Sometimes Demonstrated
Asks the right questions.	3.80	Often Demonstrated	3.76	Often Demonstrated
Provide clear and specific questions.	2.60	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.60	Sometimes Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	3.21	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.18	Sometimes Demonstrated

As shown in Table 7, an average weighted mean of 3.21 as rated by teachers and 3.18 as evaluated by school heads revealed that teachers in Las Nieves District II sometimes ask questions appropriate to the level of students during teaching – learning process. It was also found out that teachers always give students enough time to respond with a highest weighted mean of 4.53. In addition, the school heads with the highest weighted mean of 4.48 observed that teachers often give students enough time to respond. On the other hand, the

lowest weighted means of 2.56 and 2.54 as rated by teachers and school heads respectively, pointed out that teachers sometimes provide clear intent in questioning. This implies that good way of questioning will motivate the students to answer with confidence.

Sockalingam (2011) affirmed the result that teachers need to have a clear intent for questioning and also learn to ask the right questions. To guide students on the learning process, it is essential to question on learning outcome as well as students' thinking and learning processes. Through this, the student will learn to answer the questions being thrown to them without hesitation and thus, provide quality instruction.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Teaching Modelling

Table 8 shows that teachers sometimes provide quality of instruction as to teaching modelling with an average weighted mean of 2.83 as rated by the teachers and 2.77 as rated by the school heads. The highest weighted means of 3.52 and 3.50 indicate that teachers often use application tasks as bridge to new lessons while the lowest weighted means of 2.38 and 2.35 revealed that teachers seldom encourage students to use problem-solving strategies. This implies that differentiated modelling activities will encourage different types of learners to demonstrate what they have learned in the class.

The Room 241 Team (2015) has a similar finding that each student is different, and when it comes to learning styles, the ones that prove the most

Table 8

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Teaching Modelling

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Encourage students to use problem-solving strategies.	2.38	Seldom Demonstrated	2.35	Seldom Demonstrated
Use different strategies in order to keep different groups of students involved in classroom interactions.	3.25	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.18	Sometimes Demonstrated
Promote the idea of teaching modelling strategies among students.	2.47	Seldom Demonstrated	2.44	Seldom Demonstrated
Give different types of modelling activities to meet different learning needs of students.	2.44	Seldom Demonstrated	2.31	Seldom Demonstrated
Demonstrate new strategies.	2.92	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.86	Sometimes Demonstrated
Use application tasks as bridge to new lessons.	3.52	Often Demonstrated	3.50	Often Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.83	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.77	Sometimes Demonstrated

effective depend on who is being taught. One of the ways in which teachers can maximize the effectiveness of their time in the classroom is to rotate the types of instruction that they're using, making sure that there is a mix of strategies that might work well for different students. By combining a few different types of

modelling activities, teachers make the classroom a dynamic place to learn and keep their students engaged with the modelling activities.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Application of Learnings

Table 9

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Application of Learnings

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Use challenging activities to widen knowledge development.	2.48	Seldom Demonstrated	2.45	Seldom Demonstrated
Provide differentiated exercises for learners' learning diversity.	1.48	Not Demonstrated at All	1.47	Not Demonstrated at All
Provide students with enough application opportunities.	3.01	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.00	Sometimes Demonstrated
Allow students to apply learnings individually or in small group.	3.88	Often Demonstrated	3.85	Often Demonstrated
Help the students experience learning in a dynamic way.	3.34	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.37	Sometimes Demonstrated
Provide exercises that is fun and enjoyable.	2.87	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.95	Sometimes Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.84	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.85	Sometimes Demonstrated

Table 9 reflects the teacher respondents' quality of instruction as to application. It revealed that teachers sometimes applied different means to

transfer learning towards students with an average weighted mean of 2.84 as rated by teachers and 2.85 as weighed by school head. With the highest weighted means of 3.88 and 3.85 respectively, teachers often allow students to apply learnings individually or in small group. The lowest weighted means of 1.48 and 1.47 indicate that teachers rarely provide differentiated exercises during teaching-learning process. This implies that by allowing the students to experience what they have learned, makes the learning meaningful.

Relajo-Howell (2017) stressed that by permitting the students to apply what they have learned will tend to master those learning.

In addition, it was affirmed by Slavin (2014) that collaboration is the process by which learners interact in small groups to learn. Further, he stated that within a group, different strengths and weaknesses were shown, thus, helping one another will lead to significant learning.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Classroom as a Learning Environment

Table 10 reflects the quality of instruction as to classroom as a learning environment. Teachers of Las Nieves District II sometimes demonstrated this during teaching – learning process with an average weighted mean of 3.16 and 3.13 as rated by teachers and school heads respectively. The highest weighted means of 3.88 and 3.86 revealed that teachers often encourage students to respect one another inside the classroom. With the lowest weighted means of 2.24 and 2.22 for both raters, revealed that teachers seldom bring real world to

the classroom setting. This implies that maintaining and engaging students in the real world setting will help develop significant learning.

Table 10

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Classroom as a Learning Environment

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Enough attention and opportunity to students to participate in the lesson.	3.51	Often Demonstrated	3.49	Sometimes Demonstrated
Encourage collaboration and competition among students during the teaching – learning process.	2.81	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.79	Sometimes Demonstrated
Provide and explain classroom rules especially when dealing with teacher student interaction and student-student interaction and students' misbehavior.	2.93	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.91	Sometimes Demonstrated
Establish and implement classroom rules and regulations to avoid misbehavior.	3.59	Often Demonstrated	3.48	Sometimes Demonstrated
Bring real world to the classroom setting.	2.24	Seldom Demonstrated	2.22	Seldom Demonstrated
Encourage respect for one another inside the classroom.	3.88	Often Demonstrated	3.86	Often Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	3.16	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.13	Sometimes Demonstrated

This finding was affirmed by Luukkonen (2011) that bringing the real world inside the classroom is like breaking distinctions among texts and real – life objects. Students will learn best when they can see, touch or smell the object itself.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Management of Time

Table 11

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Management of Time

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Make sure that every student is engaged on task during the teaching – learning process.	2.40	Seldom Demonstrated	2.43	Seldom Demonstrated
Allocate appropriate lengths of time for each activity.	2.47	Seldom Demonstrated	2.44	Seldom Demonstrated
Ensure that opportunities to learn are provided throughout the lesson.	3.18	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.13	Sometimes Demonstrated
Allot different lengths of time for different groups of students.	2.42	Seldom Demonstrated	2.44	Seldom Demonstrated
Consider objectives to be time bounded.	2.45	Seldom Demonstrated	2.40	Seldom Demonstrated
Provide dissimilar length of time for each tasks based on its difficulty.	1.88	Seldom Demonstrated	1.85	Seldom Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.47	Seldom Demonstrated	2.45	Seldom Demonstrated

As shown in Table 11, the average weighted mean of 2.47 as rated by teacher respondents and 2.45 as perceived by school heads revealed that teachers of Las Nieves district II seldom manage their time during the teaching and learning process. The highest weighted means of 3.18 and 3.13 indicate that teachers sometimes provide students opportunities to learn throughout the lesson. The lowest weighted mean of 1.88 and 1.85 as reflected on both raters, teachers seldom provide dissimilar length of time for each tasks based on its difficulty. This implies that time consciousness within the given tasks leads to the achievement of set learning goals.

The result affirms Verner's (2018) idea that it is important for both teachers and learners to be time-bounded. But the necessities are within the teachers' control. Teacher gives their students instructions at the start of each activity, and make sure that the instructions are brief but clear.

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Assessment

The results in Table 12, on assessment shows that both the teacher respondents and school heads agreed that teachers in Las Nieves District II oftentimes show positive output with an average weighted mean of 3.50 and 3.51 respectively. Also, with the highest weighted means of 4.31 and 4.30 respectively for both raters, revealed that teachers often provided students the feedback on their performances. The lowest weighted means of 2.60 and 2.63, revealed that teachers sometimes ask students to reflect on the lesson and write insights on

what they've learned. This implies that good assessment of students' knowledge will lead to two-way benefit of learning.

Table 12

Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction as to Assessment

Elements	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Provide open-ended questions that get them writing/talking.	3.07	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.10	Sometimes Demonstrated
Use appropriate techniques to assess students' knowledge and skills gained.	3.75	Often Demonstrated	3.74	Often Demonstrated
Analyze test results to identify students' needs.	3.53	Often Demonstrated	3.48	Sometimes Demonstrated
Ask students to reflect on the lesson and write insights on what they've learned.	2.60	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.63	Sometimes Demonstrated
Emerge students ask questions of one another about an essential question, topic, or selected text.	3.77	Often Demonstrated	3.76	Often Demonstrated
Assessment feedback is provided to the students immediately.	4.31	Often Demonstrated	4.30	Often Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	3.50	Often Demonstrated	3.51	Often Demonstrated

Guskey and Jung (2013) reinforced the result that teachers who develop appropriate assessments, provide corrective instruction, and give students

second chances to demonstrate success can improve their instruction and help students learn.

Summary on the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Table 13

Summary on the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Factors	Weighted mean (teacher)	Verbal description	Weighted mean (school head)	Verbal description
Orientation of Learners	2.36	Seldom Demonstrated	2.35	Seldom Demonstrated
Structuring of Lesson	2.91	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.89	Sometimes Demonstrated
Questioning	3.21	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.18	Sometimes Demonstrated
Teaching Modelling	2.83	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.77	Sometimes Demonstrated
Application of Learnings	2.84	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.85	Sometimes Demonstrated
Classroom as a Learning Environment	3.16	Sometimes Demonstrated	3.13	Sometimes Demonstrated
Management of Time	2.47	Seldom Demonstrated	2.45	Seldom Demonstrated
Assessment	3.50	Often Demonstrated	3.51	Often Demonstrated
Average Weighted Mean	2.91	Sometimes Demonstrated	2.89	Sometimes Demonstrated

Table 13, shows the summary on the factors affecting quality of instruction of teachers during the teaching-learning process. It indicates that teachers in Las

Nieves District II sometimes demonstrated the eight factors affecting quality of instruction with average weighted mean of 2.91 and 2.89 respectively. Also with the highest weighted mean of 3.50 and 3.51 revealed that teachers often provide students with good assessment. The lowest weighted mean of 2.36 and 2.35 respectively, it found out that students are not well – oriented with the objectives during teaching – learning process. This denotes that it is much more reliable to enhance these eight factors affecting quality of instruction to help students attain quality learning.

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference between the teachers' and school heads' responses as to the factors affecting quality of instruction?

Significant Difference between Teachers' and School Head's Responses on Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Table 14 shows the test of significant difference between the responses of the teachers and the school heads of Las Nieves District II on the factors affecting quality of instruction. A Mann Whitney U-test revealed that there is no significant difference between the responses of the teachers and the school heads of Las Nieves District II on factors affecting quality of instruction as to orientation of learners ($U=4072$, $p=0.846$), structuring of lesson ($U=4018.5$, $p=0.729$), questioning ($U=4028.5$, $p=0.750$), teaching modelling ($U=3886.5$, $p=0.471$), application of learnings ($U=4123$, $p=0.960$), classroom as a learning environment ($U=4140.5$, $p=1.000$), management of time (4004.5 , $p=0.699$) and

assessment ($U=4121$, $p=0.956$). This implies that both teachers and school heads have the same responses on the factors affecting quality of instruction of teachers, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 14

Test of Significant Difference between Teachers' and School Heads' Responses

Factors	U	P	Decision
Orientation of Learners	4072.000	.846	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Structuring of Lesson	4018.500	.729	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Questioning	4028.500	.750	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Teaching Modelling	3886.500	.471	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Application of Learnings	4123.000	.960	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Classroom as a Learning Environment	4140.500	1.000	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Management of Time	4004.500	.699	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.
Assessment	4121.000	.956	Fail to reject Ho. No significant difference.

This finding was strengthened by Bichi (2017) that the effective monitoring and evaluation of teaching is central to the continuous improvement of the quality of instruction of teachers in a school. It is essential to know the strengths of

teachers and those aspects of their practices which could be further developed. From this perspective, teacher evaluation is a vital step in the drive to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning and raise educational standards.

Problem 4. Which of the independent variables singly or in combination affects the teachers' quality of instruction?

Chi-Square Test on Age and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Table 15

Chi-Square Test on Age and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Factors	χ^2	<i>P</i>	Decision
Orientation of Learners	3.948 ^a	.915	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Structuring of Lesson	7.362 ^a	.289	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Questioning	4.972 ^a	.547	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Teaching Modelling	.985 ^a	.986	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Application of Learnings	2.982 ^a	.811	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Classroom as a Learning Environment	.319 ^a	.956	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Management of Time	5.861 ^a	.439	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Assessment	14.156 ^a	.117	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.

Table 15 shows a chi-square test and was used to determine the significant association between the age of teacher respondents and the factors affecting quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time, and assessment in Las Nieves District II. The test revealed that there is no significant association between age of the teachers and the factors affecting quality of instruction with all the $p > 0.05$. This implies that age does not affect the teachers' quality of instruction.

Bodhe and Jankar (2013) strengthened the result that age regardless of young or old has potential to be a good teacher. Furthermore, as long as teachers can teach enthusiastically with effective communication and problem solving skills, there should be no problem.

Chi-Square Test on Educational Attainment and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Table 16 shows a chi - square test and was used to determine the significant association between the educational attainment of teachers and the factors affecting quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time, and assessment in Las Nieves District II. The test revealed that educational attainment of teachers had significant association with the factors affecting quality of instruction. This implies that educational attainment of teachers does affect the teaching performance of

Table 16

Chi-Square Test on Educational Attainment and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Factors	χ^2	P	Decision
Orientation of Learners	12.987 ^a	.043	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Structuring of Lesson	11.637 ^a	.020	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Questioning	9.891 ^a	.042	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Teaching Modelling	9.920 ^a	.041	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Application of Learnings	13.932 ^a	.007	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Classroom as a Learning Environment	11.900 ^a	.003	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Management of Time	9.500 ^a	.049	Reject Ho. Has significant association.
Assessment	6.701 ^a	.035	Reject Ho. Has significant association.

teachers in Las Nieves District II.

The result is similar to Vandersall, Vruwink, and LaVenía (2012) that teachers who earn master's degrees demonstrate greater teaching effectiveness than those who don't. The study found that students whose teachers held a master's degree performed better in reading and writing tests. In addition, Horn and Jang (2017) stated that teachers who earn their advanced degrees show a

deep level of understanding and commitment to the profession, allowing them to modify curriculum goals, adjust teaching methods, and enter leadership positions to enact the system-wide changes in education they wish to see.

Chi-Square Test on Years in Service and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Table 17

Chi-Square Test on Years in Service and the Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Factors	χ^2	<i>P</i>	Decision
Orientation of Learners	2.926 ^a	.540	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Structuring of Lesson	6.235 ^a	.949	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Questioning	4.196 ^a	.685	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Teaching Modelling	2.886 ^a	.664	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Application of Learnings	3.698 ^a	.139	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Classroom as a Learning Environment	.892 ^a	.848	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Management of Time	2.564 ^a	.534	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.
Assessment	3.257 ^a	.777	Fail to reject Ho. No significant association.

In Table 17, a chi - square test was used to determine the significant association between the years in service of teachers and the factors affecting the

quality of instruction as to orientation of learners, structuring of lesson, questioning, teaching modelling, application of learnings, classroom as a learning environment, management of time, and assessment in Las Nieves District II. The test revealed that years on service of teachers had no significant association with the factors affecting quality of instruction. This implies that years in service does not affect teachers' quality of instruction.

The result was strengthened by Sawchuk (2015) that though at first, years in service has impact to quality instruction, but later on, gained experiences would not be enough to associate with the quality of teaching.

In addition, Huang and Moon (2010) stated that total years of service was not significantly associated with teachers' performance as they noted that while 3% of the examined studies actually indicated a negative association between teachers' years of experience and teachers' performance, and 30% indicated a positive association which usually for only the first few years of teaching, the majority 67% showed no correlation between teachers' years of experience and teachers' performance.

Problem 5. What intervention program can be made based on the findings of the study?

Title: School Based Development Training on Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction

Rationale: Modern society demands high quality teaching and learning from teachers. Using effective instructional strategies that are learner centered, engaging and relevant to the goals and needs of each learner, quality of instruction will be boost. Thus, teachers have to possess a great deal of knowledge and skills with regard to both teaching and learning practices in order to meet those demands and standards of quality instruction.

Findings of this study revealed that teachers of Las Nieves District II, seldom or sometimes demonstrated the teacher level factors affecting quality of instruction. On this note, teachers need an intervention program to refresh them with what are expected from them in order to deliver quality instruction to learners. This could be made possible through the Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions.

Participants: Public Elementary Teachers and School Heads of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte

ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

Objectives	Content	Strategy	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Supplies/ Equipments	Evaluation
Factors Affecting Quality of Instruction						
A. Orientation of Learners						
1. Acquire skills in orienting the students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purposes of the Orientation • Ways of Orienting Learners 	4A's	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Project or - Laptop 	How should orientation of the lesson be done?

B. Structuring of Lesson						
1. Gain knowledge on structuring the lesson.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bloom's Taxonomy • Procedure in lesson structuring 	Group Summarizing	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Activity Sheets - Project or - Laptop 	How are lessons sequenced?
C. Questioning						
1. Enhance the art of questioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Order Thinking Skills • Principles of giving feedback 	Peer Discussion and Group Simulation	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Video Clips - Laptop 	How is the art of questioning of teacher?
D. Teaching Modelling						
1. Improve teaching strategies of learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different Types of Teaching Modelling Strategies by Subject 	Demo Teaching or Role Playing	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Instructional Materials - Project or - Laptop 	How should teachers use the different teaching strategies?
E. Application of Learnings						
1. Enrich knowledge in providing activities appropriate to the learning needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Styles • Differentiated activities 	Carousel Cooperative Learning	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Instructional Materials - Project or - Laptop 	How should teachers categorized different activities?
F. Classroom as a Learning Environment						
1. Strengthen competency in making good	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles of Classroom Management • Tips on 	4A's	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Realia - Project or - Laptop 	How should teachers make a good learning

learning environment	Classroom Management					environment?
G. Management of Time						
1. Adapt appropriate strategies on managing time in a class.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategies on Time Management • Do's and Don'ts in Time Management 	5E's	1 st Semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Person - School Heads - Teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Print-outs - Puzzles - Project or - Laptop 	How should management of time be done?

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the pertinent aspects of this study. It reflects the findings obtained and the conclusions derived based on the gathered data. It also offers some recommendations that emerged as a result of the investigation.

Summary

The following findings are the results of the interpretation of the gathered data:

The investigation revealed that majority of the respondents belong to middle age bracket. As to educational attainment, most of the respondents were not able to pursue post graduate studies. As to years in service, most of the respondents were new to the teaching profession.

Based on the results, teachers in Las Nieves District II sometimes demonstrated the factors affecting quality of instruction as rated by teachers and school heads. It was further found out that teachers seldom orient their learners on the objectives of the lesson and manage their time as rated by teachers and school heads. Further, teachers sometimes prepare well-structured lessons for learners and ask questions appropriate to the level of students during teaching – learning process. Similarly, teachers sometimes provide quality of instruction as to teaching modelling and in guiding students apply learnings. Data also revealed that teachers sometimes set the mood of the classroom as a learning environment and let students experience the real world setting inside the

classroom. Both raters revealed that teachers often but not always provide good assessment on students' learnings.

There is no significant difference between the teachers' and school heads' responses on the factors affecting quality of instruction. Lastly, the study revealed that among the independent variables, only educational attainment has significant association to the factors affecting quality of instruction.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of this study, the researcher concludes that:

Majority of the teacher respondents were middle-aged. Most of the respondents were not able to pursue post-graduate studies. Majority of the respondents were less experienced in the field of teaching.

Teachers in Las Nieves District II need to enhance their knowledge and skills in teaching in order to deliver quality instruction. Upgrading their instructional competencies will promote quality student learning and increase academic performance. There is no significant difference between teachers' and school heads' responses as to the eight factors affecting quality of instruction. It shows that school heads are keen enough in monitoring the performances of their teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

DepEd Top Officials. The Department of Education may conduct trainings on factors affecting quality of instruction.

School Administrators. School administrators must intensify instructional supervision and give feedback on the performances of teachers so that teachers are guided on their areas of improvement.

Teachers. Teachers are encouraged to undertake trainings which would improve their competencies with regards to quality instruction.

Future Researchers. A further study may be made by the future researchers to explore more variables which are not included in the present study.

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APPENDIX A
LETTER REQUEST WITH APPROVAL

January 10, 2020

ROMEO O. APROVECHAR, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent
Division of Agusan del Norte
Butuan City, Agusan del Norte

Sir:

Greeting of peace and bounty!

The undersigned is on the process of undertaking a study entitled, **TEACHER LEVEL FACTORS AFFECTING QUALITY OF INSTRUCTION IN LAS NIEVES DISTRICT II, DIVISION OF AGUSAN DEL NORTE** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Arts in Education at Northern Mindanao Colleges, Inc.

In this connection, the researcher would humbly ask permission to distribute survey questionnaires to the public elementary teachers and school heads of Las Nieves District II, Division of Agusan del Norte in order to obtain the necessary information needed for the said study.

Your kind consideration to this request is highly appreciated.

Thank you so much and God bless!

Respectfully yours,

ANGEL ROY A. LONGAKIT
Researcher

NOTED:

DR. REBECCA V. DELAPUZ, CESO IV
Dean of Graduate School, NMCI

APPROVED:

ROMEO O. APROVECHAR, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent

APPENDIX B

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

TEACHER LEVEL FACTORS AFFECTING QUALITY OF INSTRUCTION
IN LAS NIEVES DISTRICT II, DIVISION OF AGUSAN DEL NORTE

Name (optional): _____ Date: _____
School: _____

Block I. Respondents' Profile

Directions. Check the box that best describes you.

1. Age

- 20-30 years old
 31-40 years old
 41-50 years old
 51-60 years old

2. Educational Attainment

- Post Graduate (Ph.D. Degree Holder / Master's Degree Holder)
 College Graduate
 With MA Units

3. Years in Service

- 1-10 years
 11-20 years
 21-30 years
 31-40 years

Block II. Elements of Quality Instruction

Directions: Please answer the following items by checking the appropriate box. Please be guided by the scale below.

Rating	Verbal Description
5	Always Demonstrated
4	Often Demonstrated
3	Sometimes Demonstrated
2	Seldom Demonstrated
1	Not Demonstrated at All

FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Orientation of Learners					
1.1. Provide students with aims/goals of lessons to take place.					
1.2. Link the day's lesson to previous lesson or students' daily life.					
1.3. Present the aims in different stages in accordance with the flow of the activities.					
1.4. Offer clear and understandable aims for students.					
1.5. Provide different ways of presenting the aims in response to different background of students.					
1.6. Challenge students to identify reasons for an activity.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
2. Structuring of Lessons					
2.1. Begin with overview of objectives.					
2.2. Present the structure of the lesson.					
2.3. Explain the link among different activities.					
2.4. Signal the transition between one phase/activity and others.					
2.5. Outline content of the lesson.					
2.6. Review main ideas.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
3. Questioning					
3.1. Raise questions at appropriate difficulty levels.					
3.2. Has clear intent in questioning.					
3.3. Give students enough time to respond.					
3.4. Give positive and constructive comments or feedback to students' responses.					
3.5. Asks the right questions.					
3.6. Provide clear and specific questions.					

FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
4. Teaching Modelling					
4.1. Encourage students to use problem-solving strategies.					
4.2. Use different strategies in order to keep different groups of students involved in classroom interactions.					
4.3. Promote the idea of teaching modelling strategies among students.					
4.4. Give different types of modeling activities to meet different learning needs of students.					
4.5. Demonstrate new strategies.					
4.6. Use application tasks as bridge to new lessons.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
5. Application of Learning					
5.1. Use challenging activities to widen knowledge development.					
5.2. Provide differentiated exercises for learners' learning diversity.					
5.3. Provide students with enough application opportunities.					
5.4. Allow students to apply learnings individually or in small group.					
5.5. Help the students experience learning in a dynamic way.					
5.6. Provide exercises that is fun and enjoyable.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
6. Classroom as a Learning Environment					
6.1. Enough attention and opportunity to students to participate in the lesson.					
6.2. Encourage collaboration and competition among students during the teaching – learning process.					

6.3. Provide and explain classroom rules especially when dealing with teacher student interaction and student-student interaction and students' misbehavior.					
6.4. Establish and implement classroom rules and regulations to avoid misbehavior.					
6.5. Bring real world to the classroom setting.					
6.6. Encourage respect for one another inside the classroom.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
7. Management of Time					
7.1. Make sure that every student is engaged on task during the teaching – learning process.					
7.2. Allocate appropriate lengths of time for each activity.					
7.3. Ensure that opportunities to learn are provided throughout the lesson.					
7.4. Allot different lengths of time for different groups of students.					
7.5. Consider objectives to be time bounded.					
7.6. Provide dissimilar length of time for each tasks based on its difficulty.					
FACTORS / ELEMENTS	5	4	3	2	1
8. Assessment					
8.1. Provide open-ended questions that get them writing/talking.					
8.2. Use appropriate techniques to assess students' knowledge and skills gained.					
8.3. Analyze test results to identify students' needs.					
8.4. Ask students to reflect on the lesson and write insights on what they've learned.					
8.5. Emerge students ask questions of one another about an essential question, topic, or selected text.					
8.6. Assessment feedback is provided to the students immediately.					

APPENDIX C

MAP OF THE RESEARCH LOCALE

Figure 2. Map of the Elementary Schools of Las Nieves II

APPENDIX D

TEST OF NORMALITY

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Z	p	Distribution	Comparative Analysis Test
Orientation of Learners	1.57	0.015	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Structuring of Lessons	1.58	0.014	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Questioning	2.24	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Teaching Modelling	2.23	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Application of Learnings	2.24	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Classroom as a Learning Environment	2.08	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Management of Time	2.10	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test
Assessment	2.16	0.000	Non - Parametric	Mann - Whitney U-test

Note: If $p > 0.05$, the data distribution is parametric. Otherwise, non - parametric.

APPENDIX E

CURRICULUM VITAE

PERSONAL DATA

Name : Angel Roy A. Longakit
Nickname : Roy
Date of Birth : February 25, 1995
Place of Birth : Tagum City, Davao del Norte
Home Address : Brgy. Sto. Niño, Magallanes, Agusan del Norte
Parents : Romeo P. Longakit
Marlyn A. Longakit
Civil Status : Single
Occupation : Professional Teacher
School Assigned : E.G. Montilla National High School

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Graduate Studies : Northern Mindanao Colleges, Inc.
Atega St., Cabadbaran City
(November 2017 – Present)
Tertiary : Northern Mindanao Colleges, Inc.
Atega St., Cabadbaran City
June 2012 – April 2016
Secondary : Fr. Urios Academy of Magallanes, Inc.

Buhang, Magallanes, Agusan del Norte
(June 2007 – March 2011)

Elementary

: Buhang Elementary School
Buhang, Magallanes, Agusan del Norte
(June 2001 – March 2007)

Eligibility

: Licensure Examination for Teachers
(September 2016)

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

2017 - Present

: E.G. Montilla National High School
Secondary School Teacher
Brgy. E.G. Montilla, Las Nieves,
Agusan del Norte

2016 – 2017

: Fr. Urios Academy of Magallanes, Inc.
Secondary School teacher
Brgy. Buhang, Magallanes, Agusan del
Norte

TRAININGS AND SEMINARS

National Level

: Computer Systems Servicing NCII
Candelaria Institute of Cabadbaran
City
2017

: Computer Programming NC IV
Northern Mindanao Colleges, Inc.
2012

: Food and Beverage Servicing NC II
Northern Mindanao School of Fisheries
Magallanes Campus
2011

: Computer Hardware Servicing NC II
Northern Mindanao School of Fisheries

Magallanes Campus
2011

Regional Level

: Caraga Regional
Athletics Meet Training for Coaches
Barobo, Surigao del Sur
2017

MERITS AND AWARDS RECEIVED

Division Level

: Third Place – 2019 Table Tennis
(Secondary-Coach)

APPENDIX F
DOCUMENTATION

**Preparation for Thesis Proposal
Co-advisees and Advisers**

**Preparation for Thesis Proposal
Co-advisees and Advisers**

My Respondents

My Respondents

My Respondents

**Interpretation of Results
with My Statistician**

Working with My Adviser

My Respondents

My Respondents

Elementary Schools

My Respondents